

On Network Collaboration in CLARIAH

In the context of “Networks for Impact enabling change Libraries - Laws - Leadership”

During the World Library and Information Congress [IFLA2023](#), on Tuesday 22nd of August 2023, the National Committee of the Netherlands hosted a plenary session on the impact of cooperating in networks to achieve impact and to enable change. Several participants presented examples of how they form, facilitate and strengthen networks in their respective fields in order to battle the complex societal challenges. The goal of the session was to show that it is possible to cooperate in this way, but that it requires fundamental different ways of working, organising and sharing responsibility. It requires fundamental new leadership.

Roeland Ordelman, CTO of CLARIAH reflected in his contribution on network collaboration in CLARIAH:

CLARIAH Research Infrastructure

Since 2012 we are working on a common, digital research infrastructure for the arts & humanities funded by the Dutch Research Council (NWO). The goal is to foster digital scholarship by enabling seamless access to, and also digital tools to work with, the extremely rich and varied data sets that live in our collective Dutch knowledge infrastructure, especially including also libraries, archives and museums. Essentially, we are working on, or contributing to the Digital Transformation of our national knowledge infrastructure: bringing it *inline* with the contemporary digital needs and methods. Enabling for example advanced search, large-scale analysis of data, connecting distributed data sets, and cross-platform annotation of data sets.

We know however that fostering Digital Transformation is already complex on an institutional level. It becomes even more difficult when we need to align this transformation with multiple institutions having different priorities, cultures and levels of digital literacy and operational skills or capacity. We also need to be aware of different needs and digital skills across the disciplines we want to support. We need to align internationally, enabling collaboration and connection with European research infrastructures. Monitoring ICT research and innovation with the help of the more technically-oriented disciplines in our network is also crucial to align strategically with the fast evolving ICT landscape, most notably developments in artificial intelligence. And last but not least, the Digital Transformation needs to be aligned with the various industry partners the institutions are working with in order to foster interoperability and long-term sustainability.

Building a common research infrastructure and aiming for this alignment is very ambitious.

Stakeholder Readiness

To move forward together, we need to add some pragmatics to these ambitions and put the “we” more central. Practically, this means paying a bit more attention to the various contexts in which the project operates. Put the focus on project outputs and deliverables –typically

defined in a project's Workplan– in a broader scope, to what we sometimes refer to as “Stakeholder Readiness”: how can we fit in with the needs, values, expectations, mission, goals, organisation and requirements of the various stakeholders, so that we can improve the way we collaborate and maximise impact of the project. Two examples:

1. Can we **collaborate differently**? E.g., align agendas and development roadmaps, bringing developers, data specialist and users together, could we pool experts in cross-institutional teams.
2. Can we **maximize impact**? E.g., does a tool we build really provide the expected value for the intended end-user? Is the value that the tool provides inline with the goals of an organisation? Is the organisation capable of maintaining this tool? Does it have the expertise or capacity to provide support? Etc.

In order to be able to approach a project this way we need to better understand and discuss the needs, values, expectations, mission, goals, organisation, and requirements of the various individual stakeholders.

Current activities

We try to bring communities together as much as possible to stimulate interaction, discussion, co-creation and co-development: regular developer days, open demo days, data curation workshops, panel discussions, speed-dates, etc.

On a more managerial level we make a stand for the alignment of roadmaps and goals, e.g., by fostering collaboration with other networks such as the Digital Heritage Network, and embracing initiatives such as National Summit Digital Infrastructure and a CTO-summit with Industry partners.

Practically, we attempt to evaluate Stakeholder Readiness on product level: in addition to say something about the Technology Readiness Level of a product, we aim for measuring Stakeholder Readiness Level.

One of our biggest practical challenges currently is: how can we reduce workload and make efficiently use of sparse human resources. I imagine this could also be an incentive for seeking alignment together.